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Review Article

**PERSPECTIVE OF HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS IN
PAKISTAN ON COVID-19; AN OVERVIEW**¹Dr Asif Islam, ²Dr Zainab Younus, ³Arif Ahmad, ⁴Ayesha Younas¹MBBS, FCPS Medicine, Evercare hospital Lahore, drasifsaldera@yahoo.com²MBBS, DA (Diploma in Anesthesia), Evercare hospital Lahore, duaa.iqbalian@yahoo.com³Lecturer at National University of Modern Language, Lahore, arifahmad445@gmail.com⁴Lecturer at Kips campus Lahore, ayeshayounas356@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Background: The 2019-2020 Coronavirus pandemic also name as (COVID-19) is caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus2. The outbreak was first identified in Wuhan, Hubei china. From where it spread to the rest of the world. Now more than 177 countries, report the cases of corona pandemic with large number of corona cases and deaths.

Objective: This study highlights the available information, spreading patterns, and healing patterns in Pakistan from the perspective of doctors.

Research design: Researchers apply quantitative method. Data is collected through survey from 200 doctors, in Lahore Pakistan, through random sampling technique, which is analyzed through SPSS.

Results: This research highlight the pandemic current situation in Pakistan. This study conclude that Doctors of Pakistan are aware from the pandemic disease and its healing patterns, this research also highlight the symptoms, and healing pattern of corona virus disease in Pakistan. The implications of this paper is discussed.

Conclusion: The results of this conclude that the doctors in Pakistan are well aware of the corona virus spread pattern, pandemic, treatment options and its signs and symptoms. Though, further studies are required to determine its type and DNA pattern among patients in Pakistan. Because the global threat of COVID-19 is still emerging, improving awareness and perception among healthcare professionals is crucial. Training interventions are urgently needed to reach HCWs beyond the borders and further work is needed.

Keywords: Covid-19, Health care Professionals, pandemic, Quantitative method

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INTRODUCTION:

Coronavirus is a pandemic disease originated in china and quickly spread to more than 177 countries of the world. The First case of coronavirus was reported in 55 years old man in china on November 2019. Later in December 2019, in Wuhan city of china many people showed the symptoms of coronavirus and the number of cases suddenly increases. Due to quick and larger impact throughout the world, the coronavirus outbreak was declared as a global pandemic by the world health organization on 11 march 2020. According to report of world health organization, it took more than three month for the cases to reach 10 thousand, but only 12 days to reach 20 thousand and four days to reach 30 thousand and three days to reach 40 Lakh. So far more than fourth thousand people died due to this pandemic and the number is increasing on daily basis.

On 26 February, 2020 Pakistan confirmed first two cases of corona, one at Sindh and other at Islamabad. Both of the patients had recently returned from Iran. Now after a month, in Pakistan, number of confirm cases are 5374, and 93 people have been died due to this pandemic. According to some reports number of case are more than 12 thousand, which we have not verified due to limited testing kits.

Now china had returned to normal routine after declaring that, there is no more corona cases. In Pakistan the number of cases are increasing daily. Although government of Pakistan knew about the pandemic and its symptoms and prepare to deal with it. Still it spread in the whole Pakistan with a high speed.

Recent studies show that so far, there are no specific medicine available for controlling the corona epidemic, however some precautions such as frequently, washing hands with soap, isolation and sanitation, can help in controlling this disease. Through this way China control this epidemic and rest of the world also implement it in the form of lockdowns and force isolation. Now a days it is impossible to reach all people directly hence the onus is on the digital media to spread the information quickly.

Although Pakistan is a developing country, facing many problems such as shortage of medicine, overloaded hospitals, large number of rural population and weak organizational structure, so far Pakistan fought the corona very well and only few death cases are reported. In this digital era the IT play a crucial role, not only in highlighting the corona disease but people come forward on IT for spreading information, awareness about symptoms and causes, precautions and helping people at their door in the case of lockdown, such as Prime Minister

Tiger force, application, which will provide support to the government and beside spreading information they will identify the needy people and provide them food and medicine at their door step. Therefore, this study highlights the role of IT in Pakistan, in fighting the corona problem by spreading information among masses and controlling the epidemic.

Objectives of the study:

- To highlight the available information about corona in hospital of Pakistan
- To highlight the symptoms awareness of corona virus pandemic in patients of Pakistan
- To highlight the corona recovery patterns in patients of Pakistan.

Hypothesis

- The doctors of Pakistan have sufficient information about corona virus pandemic.
- The doctors of Pakistan have sufficient information about the symptoms of corona virus pandemic.
- The doctors of Pakistan have sufficient information about recovery patterns in patients of Pakistan.

Literature review

Coronaviruses are non-segmented positive sense RNA, belonging to the family Coronaviridae, it is also called animal virus. Now a days beside other mammals, it is broadly distributed in humans (Richman, Whitley, & Hayden, 2016). In December 2019, many cases of pneumonia emerged with unknown reasons in Wuhan, Hubei, China. Its symptoms were likely normal pneumonia. Later tracking and analysis of the pandemic indicated a novel coronavirus, which was named 2019 novel coronavirus or (2019-nCoV) (Fan et al., 2020). Initial research in china investigated that most of the infected patients were men, one family cluster was found and majority of them had been exposed to Huanan seafood market. Common systems of illness were sputum production, headache, hemoptysis and diarrhea (Huang et al., 2020). Further researches highlight that this virus infection belong to animals and I human working at the same market. All the animal isolates retain a 29-nucleotide sequence that is not found in most human isolates. So this pandemic disease transfer from animals to humans which is an exceptional case.

According to statistics of (WHO, 2020) on 1 April, 2020, so far in the world more than 872,893 coronavirus cases were reported in which 43,271 died. Similarly, in Pakistan, till 1 April 2020, total 2071 cases were reported in which 27 died and 82 recovered. Due to shortage of testing kits according to some experts, total corona active cases are above 15000 (Dawn, 2020).

METHODOLOGY:

This study applies Quantitative method in the form of survey. Researchers first develop the survey questionnaire. After that, researcher approach the doctors of Lahore Pakistan through random sampling. Researchers fill questionnaire from the target respondents.

RESULTS:

The section present results of the study. Results are presented in the form of graphs. In our study, 96% were government employees and 70% were from private sector. According to 166 HCPs, Covid-19 is the solitary cause of disease. 150 doctors replied that the mode of transmission was droplets after sneezing, 133 said infection spread by shaking and touching hands, 10 said through sexual route and 89 said that people are infected by infected objects. 152 reply yes as having symptoms of fever, cough and sore throat while 17 replied having no symptoms. 117 replied No that Covid-19 lead to death directly while 51 replied yes. 156 doctors knows the difference between isolation and quarantine while 15 don't know. 117 have stated that during isolation PPE and social protective gear is not required while 53 replied that PPE is needed during isolation period. According to 89 HCPs, Hydroxy-chloroquine have no role prophylactically while 79 stated that it have a protective role. 166 said that there is no vaccine for corona virus while 4 said about its availability while 129 said that there is

proper treatment of corona virus while 41 said there is no proper treatment. In terms of symptoms of disease after infection; 39 said that symptoms appear after 3 days, 60 said after 5 days and 104 said after 7 days. 154 stated that frequent hand washing with soap prevent spread of the disease, 157 said social distancing have important role, 139 stated face mask has a protective role in spread of disease, 115 replied disinfectant is enough, 113 said that put hands while coughing and sneezing prevent its spread while 64 testified that warm liquids prevent the spread of Covid-19. 131 replied that soap with water is enough for hand hygiene, 60 replied that sanitizer 99.9% alcohol is appropriate for hand hygiene while 59 replied that 60% alcohol sanitizer is enough. To suspect Covid-19 cases, 144 replied travel history to infected area in last 14 days is important, 149 said that contact with positive case is mandatory while 97 replied that if there are symptoms in health care worker it may be related to Covid-19. In terms of symptoms; 161 replied fever and cough are the symptoms, 150 said respiratory distress, 91 stated myalgia's, and 88 have said headache and 5 replied that blood in the stool is the symptom of corona virus. 156 were aware of the disease severity while 14 have no idea. 120 know the proper technique to use PPE while 51 have no idea. 109 HCPs have no idea of doffing and donning while 60 have idea about it. 91 doctors replied that they are not provided with the PPE at their work place while 77 said they were given personnel protective equipment.

DISCUSSION:

Currently, COVID-19 is an issue of global debate in the media and public opinion, especially among healthcare professionals and patients. With the current increase in the transition to COVID-19, the tension of everyone, including health professionals and the healthcare system, has increased, in times of public health crisis among healthcare professionals. That is why we tested the knowledge and perception of healthcare professionals in the prevention and control of COVID-19 during a global epidemic. The knowledge and perception of COVID-19 varies depending on the category of healthcare professionals. Our study revealed that healthcare professionals have enough information about COVID-19, but showed a positive perception to prevent COVID-19 contamination. We've also found that healthcare professionals use official government websites as the primary source of information about COVID-19. COVID-19 updates, published online by government officials, have been shown to have a positive impact on improving awareness. Relying on authentic sources is an important factor in transparent information about the emerging COVID-19 infection and is necessary for preparing and responding to the current situation. An important problem, however, is that most of the health care professionals use social networks as an important source of information. Currently, a wide range of information available on the Internet and this malicious unverified information can spread quickly and also manage healthcare professionals. Health authorities and scientists clearly warn that widely misinformed information on COVID-19 is a serious problem that causes xenophobia worldwide. In this context, healthcare professionals should exercise carefully assessing information about COVID-19 and using original and scientific content from information sources.

The results of this study suggest that there are significant information known by the Pakistani doctors about the COVID-19 and the depth of knowledge between SPs, especially the transmission mode and the incubation period of COVID-19. In addition, many allied healthcare professionals have enough information, believing that COVID-19 could be treated with antiviral drugs and a vaccine was found. This is fortunate because the increase in COVID-19 levels is catastrophic worldwide, and health officials provide rich resources to educate healthcare professionals to improve their knowledge

of COVID-19. As a result, our findings were satisfactory. However, healthcare officials should encourage more information about COVID-19 among healthcare professionals, including physicians. Overall, the majority of participants positively viewed COVID-19 prevention and control. However, discrepancies were found between the perceptions of health professionals among the various categories. For example, health care professionals have noticed COVID-19 symptoms for 2 to 14 days ($p < 0.05$) and more than a quarter. Medical students are not safe to eat meat during an epidemic. Allied healthcare professionals believe that the flu vaccine is sufficient to prevent COVID-19. Finally, the vast majority of healthcare professionals have agreed to maintain hygiene, report recent travel history when people are sick, and recommend clean equipment used in wet markets.

CONCLUSION:

The results of this conclude that the doctors in Pakistan are well aware of the corona virus spread pattern, pandemic, treatment options and its signs and symptoms. Though, further studies are required to determine its type and DNA pattern among patients in Pakistan. Because the global threat of COVID-19 is still emerging, improving awareness and perception among healthcare professionals is crucial. Training interventions are urgently needed to reach HCWs beyond the borders and further work is needed.

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